

INFLUENCE OF TRANSVERSE-SHEAR AND LARGE-DEFORMATION EFFECTS ON THE LOW-SPEED IMPACT RESPONSE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

Damodar R. Ambur* and James H. Starnes, Jr.**
NASA Langley Research Center
Hampton, Virginia, USA

Chunchu B. Prasad***
Analytical Services and Materials, Inc.
Hampton, Virginia, USA

ABSTRACT

An analytical procedure based on a small-deformation theory with transverse-shear effects has been used to predict the transient response of simply supported, rectangular laminated composite plates subjected to impact loads by airgun-propelled or dropped-weight impactors. This procedure is general enough to determine the contact force, out-of-plane deflections, and in-plane strains and stresses at any plate location due to an impact force at any plate location. The results of experimental and analytical studies are compared for quasi-isotropic laminates. The results indicate that including transverse-shear effects in the analysis for predicting the impact response of laminated plates is important. The influence of large deformations on plate response is investigated by comparing analytical and experimental results for quasi-isotropic laminates with different thicknesses and impact energy levels. The results of this study indicate that large-deformation effects influence the response of both 24- and 32-ply laminated plates even for small impact energy levels and that a geometrically nonlinear analysis is required for predicting the impact response accurately.

INTRODUCTION

The effect of low-speed impact damage on the compression strength of laminated composite structures has been studied extensively by many researchers over the past several years. Test data show that the compression strength of composite structures can be reduced significantly by low-speed impact damage, even if the damage is not detectable by visual inspection. Current damage-tolerance design criteria for compression-loaded composite airframe structures are related to the impact energy or to the depth of the dent in the specimen caused by the impact event. Many of the researchers who investigated the transient response of laminated composite plates used either an airgun-propelled projectile or a dropped weight to impact the specimens. The specimen support conditions were also different for many of the investigations. For an airgun impact test, a projectile of a given diameter and material is propelled at a given speed with a compressed-air apparatus to generate an impact condition that simulates impact of an aircraft structure by runway debris and hail stones. The dropped-weight impact test uses a weight of a given mass and material dropped from a

* Senior Aerospace Engineer, Aircraft Structures Branch.

** Head, Aircraft Structures Branch.

*** Research Engineer.

preselected height to generate an impact condition that simulates impact of the structure by a dropped tool. While the results of these studies all indicate that low-speed impact damage can degrade the compression strength of composite structures, there are enough differences in the results to indicate that a consistent analytical representation of the response of a composite structure to low-speed impact by a projectile or impactor is still needed. A consistent analytical representation of the response of a composite structure to low-speed impact and the resulting initiation of damage in that structure should account for different structural, impactor and laminate parameters. These parameters include impactor mass, size and speed; specimen or target geometry, materials, laminate stacking sequence, laminate thickness, and boundary or support conditions; and the relative magnitudes of the impactor and target masses. Earlier analytical studies that were correlated with experimental results either focused on composite structures that were impacted by a relatively large mass at low impact speeds (e.g., refs. 1-5) or on composite structures that were impacted by a relatively small mass at high impact speeds (e.g., ref. 6).

In the present paper, an analysis procedure that was developed by the authors in Reference 7 has been used to determine the impact response of laminated composite plates. This procedure is general enough to include all of the significant structural and impactor parameters. A first-order shear-deformation theory is used in this analysis to represent properly any local short-wave-length bending transient response phenomena that may occur. The impact force has been idealized as a load that is locally distributed over a small area of the plate with a cosine-cosine distribution. The size of the loaded area is determined by an iterative procedure that accounts for the changes in the contact area between the impactor and the plate as the dynamic response of the plate develops. The importance of using the correct contact area to predict the response of the plate accurately is illustrated in Reference 7. The contact force, out-of-plane deflections, and in-plane stresses and strains at any plate location due to an impact force at any plate location are determined using a Fourier expansion and the Timoshenko small-increment method. In the present paper, analytical results are compared with experimental data for 24-, 32- and 48-ply [45/0/-45/90]_{NS} quasi-isotropic laminates made from a graphite-epoxy material system and subjected to low-speed impact by both airgun-propelled and dropped-weight impactors. The influence of transverse-shear deformation on the plate response is discussed for the two types of impactors. The effect of large deformations on 24-, 32- and 48-ply plates with two different types of boundary conditions is also discussed.

Identification of commercial products in the present paper is used to describe the test specimens adequately and does not constitute endorsement, expressed or implied, by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration or the publisher of these proceedings.

EXPERIMENTS

Test Specimens and Experimental Setup

The specimens tested in this investigation were fabricated from commercially available Hercules, Inc. AS4 unidirectional graphite fiber tapes preimpregnated with 3502 epoxy resin. The mechanical properties for the AS4/3502 graphite-epoxy material system are as follows: longitudinal extensional modulus, $E_1=137.8$ GPa; transverse extensional modulus, $E_2=8.96$ GPa; in-plane shear modulus, $G_{12}=5.99$ GPa; transverse shear moduli, $G_{23}=3.51$ GPa and $G_{13}=5.99$ GPa; and major Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{12}=0.3$. Unidirectional tapes were laid up to form 24-, 32- and 48-ply [45/0/-45/90]_{NS} quasi-isotropic laminated plates and cured in an autoclave using the resin manufacturer's recommended procedures. The resulting plates were ultrasonically inspected to establish specimen quality and then machined into 12.7-cm-wide by 25.4-cm-long rectangular specimens.

Knife-edge supports were used to provide simple-support boundary conditions for the test specimens. The knife-edge supports were attached to each edge of the specimen at locations 0.635 centimeters in from each edge. Teflon tape was mounted between the specimen surface and the knife-edge supports to facilitate sliding of the specimens when loaded. Each specimen was impacted on one surface at the specimen center by either an airgun-propelled or a dropped-weight impactor. The airgun used in this study is based on the airgun described in Reference 8. The airgun-propelled impactors were 1.27-cm-diameter aluminum or steel balls that were propelled at the specimens at a given speed. The dropped-weight impactor consisted of a 1.18-kg dropped-weight assembly with an instrumented tup and 1.27- and 2.54-cm-diameter steel impactor tips. For

the dropped-weight impact tests, the dropped-weight assembly was raised to a desired height and released to impact the specimen. All specimens were instrumented with electrical resistance strain gages mounted on the specimen surface as shown in Figure 1. Force and strain gage data were recorded using a digital storage oscilloscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analytical and experimental results of this study are presented and compared in this section. Analytical results are presented for 11.43-cm-wide by 24.13-cm-long plate models since the knife-edge supports for the test specimens are located 0.635 centimeters in from the actual specimen boundaries. Thus, for a perfect central impact, the coordinates for the impact site are $x = 6.35$ cm and $y = 12.70$ cm as shown in Figure 1.

Transverse-Shear-Deformation Effects

The laminated plate longitudinal strains opposite to the point of impact by a 1.27-cm-diameter steel-ball airgun impact with 1.42 J and 2.17 J of impact energy are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), respectively, as a function of time. For the laminate subjected to 1.42 J of impact energy, the analytical strain results with and without transverse-shear-deformation effects coincide with one another and also with the experimental data represented by the open symbols for the first 10 μ sec. The data after 10 μ sec indicate that the phase of the analytical strain profiles with and without transverse-shear-deformation effects are significantly different because of the natural frequency reduction associated with including transverse-shear-deformation effects in the analysis. Although the magnitudes of the differences in strain between the experimental and analytical results with transverse-shear-deformation effects indicate a large discrepancy, the phase difference is negligible. The strain magnitudes are very sensitive to the location of the impact site, and part of this difference in strain magnitude is attributed to the difficulty in measuring the exact impact-site location for the airgun experiments. The longitudinal strain results (gage 2A in Fig. 1) for a laminate subjected to an impact energy level of 2.17 J are shown in Figure 2(b) where the experimental and analytical results correlate well when transverse-shear-deformation effects are included in the analysis. The out-of-plane deflection profile for a laminate subjected to an impact energy level of 1.42 J is shown in Figure 2(c). This curve corresponds to the time at which the maximum axial strain occurs in the plate and indicates the local nature of the plate deflection for this impact case. Even for this relatively small impact energy level, the ratio of the deflection half-wave length λ to the plate thickness h is equal to 11. The value for the ratio λ/h decreases for increasing impact energy levels and the value of this ratio corresponding to 2.95 J of impact energy is equal to 8.1. Even for isotropic materials, transverse-shear deformations affect the results by approximately 5 percent for a λ/h ratio equal to 10 (ref. 9). The results presented above are consistent with the observation that classical plate theory is generally in error for λ/h ratios less than 20 for specially orthotropic laminates and indicate that it is important to include transverse-shear-deformation effects in the airgun impact analysis. Transverse-shear-deformation effects cannot be neglected for laminated plates subjected to impacts as was suggested in reference 6.

The longitudinal strain results for plates subjected to dropped-weight impact energy level of 2.95 J and 4.10 J with a 1.27-cm-diameter steel impactor are presented in Figures 2(d) and 2(e), respectively. The strain results measured by a strain gage rosette located on the surface (see Fig. 1) opposite to the point of impact for the 2.95 J energy impact case are compared with the analytical results shown in Figure 2(d) by the solid and dashed curves. These results indicate that the response due to the dropped-weight impactor occurs over a much longer time period than the response due to the airgun-propelled impactor and that transverse shear deformations do not have a significant effect on either the magnitude or the phase of the strain response for this case. The phase is minimally affected since the impactor mass is large relative to the target mass. The longitudinal strains for a laminated plate subjected to a dropped-weight impact energy level of 4.10 J are shown in Figure 2(e). Transverse shear deformations influence only the magnitude and not the phase of the response suggesting that transverse-shear-deformation effects become important as the impact energy level is increased. The λ/h ratios calculated from the out-of-plane deflection curves corresponding to the 2.95 and 4.10 J impact energy levels are 16 and 15, respectively. Although these ratios are larger than the λ/h ratios for the airgun impact cases with lower impact energy levels, transverse-shear-deformation effects still appear to be important for the 4.10 J impact case.

Since the results of the analysis with transverse-shear-deformation effects included provide better correlation between the analytical and experimental results for both the airgun and dropped-weight impact tests, all subsequent analytical results presented in the present paper have been determined with transverse-shear-deformation effects included.

Large-Deformation Effects

Nonlinear effects associated with large deformations can influence the plate response if the out-of-plane deflections are a significant percentage of the plate thickness or if the boundary conditions restrain the in-plane deflections enough to contribute to the membrane strains. Increasing the magnitude of the impact speed can cause large deformations if the plate is thin enough. The effects of geometric nonlinearities are expected to be negligible for a simply supported 48-ply quasi-isotropic laminate subjected to either an airgun-propelled or a dropped-weight impactor if the impact energy level is less than 5.42 J, which is determined to be the threshold impact energy level for which damage is initiated in the plate. The out-of-plane deflection w of such a plate subjected to an impactor with 5.42 J of impact energy is less than 0.2 times the plate thickness h for a dropped-weight impactor and is approximately 0.063 times the plate thickness for an airgun-propelled impactor. The results of the present study indicate that a dropped-weight impact with a given impact energy level below the 5.42 J threshold causes the largest out-of-plane deflection and, hence, suggests that nonlinear effects are likely to be more pronounced for the dropped-weight impact case. As a result, only dropped-weight impact cases are investigated further in the present paper. The predicted strains in the longitudinal and lateral directions for a 48-ply (0.635-cm-thick) laminate subjected to a 5.42 J dropped-weight impactor are compared with the experimental results in Figure 3(a). The correlation between the experimental and analytical results is very good. For plates that are thinner than 0.635 cm, however, the applicability of the present small-deformation theory could be limited since the w/h ratios will typically be larger for the thinner plates than for the 48-ply laminates and will increase for increasing impact energy levels. To identify these limitations, a dropped-weight impact study was conducted for 24- and 32-ply quasi-isotropic laminated plates subjected to increasing impact energy levels. The analytical procedure described in Reference 7 was used to determine the response of simply supported 24- and 32-ply-thick, 11.43-cm-wide, 24.13-cm-long graphite-epoxy plates in terms of w/h ratios as a function of the impactor energy level. The maximum values for the w/h ratios for the 32-ply (0.425-cm-thick) specimens are 0.30, 0.45, 0.55, and 0.68 for impact energy levels of 1.36, 2.95, 4.10, and 5.42 J, respectively. The maximum w/h values corresponding to these energy levels for the 24-ply (0.325-cm-thick) specimens are 0.60, 0.88, 1.05, and 1.20, respectively. Large-deformation effects are expected to influence the plate response for w/h ratios greater than 0.5.

The longitudinal strain results for the 24-ply specimens are shown in Figures 3(b) and 3(c), and the results for the 32-ply specimens are shown in Figures 3(d) and 3(e) for dropped-weight impacts. For the 1.36 J impact energy case, the correlation between the predicted and measured strains is very good. As the impact energy level is increased to 2.95 J, there is a discrepancy between the measured and predicted strains for both specimens. This discrepancy is due to membrane effects that influence the deflection and, hence, the in-plane strains of the plate. The differences in the measured and predicted strains are approximately 13 percent for the 24-ply specimen and approximately 8 percent for the 32-ply specimen. The differences are 14.5 percent and 10 percent for the 24-ply and 32-ply laminates, respectively, for the 4.10 J impact energy case. The differences between the predicted and measured results for the 5.42 J impact energy case are 28.5 and 22.5 percent, respectively, for the two laminates. These results indicate that, even for simple-support boundary conditions, an impact energy greater than 4.10 J would require an analysis to include large-deformation effects in order to be accurate for quasi-isotropic laminates thinner than the thickness of a 32-ply specimen.

The influence of boundary conditions on the nonlinear response of both the 24- and 32-ply quasi-isotropic plates has been determined experimentally. The response of plates with all four edges simply supported is compared with the response of plates with the two long sides simply supported and the two short sides clamped. The longitudinal strains on the surface of the plate opposite to the impact site for a 24-ply specimen and the two sets of boundary conditions are compared in Figure 4(a) for 1.36 J and 2.95 J of impact energy. For the 1.36 J impact energy level, the maximum difference in the longitudinal strain magnitude between plates with different sets of boundary conditions is 17 percent. This difference for the 2.95 J energy level is 26 percent. The corresponding results for a 32-ply specimen is presented in Figure 4(b). The membrane strain

results from gages 2A and 2B shown in Figure 1 for the two impact energy levels are presented in Figure 4(c) for the 24-ply specimen. The results indicate that the membrane strains for the plate with two sides simply supported and two sides clamped are much higher than the corresponding strains for the plate with all four sides simply supported. These results indicate that nonlinear effects and actual boundary conditions should be accounted for when studying the impact response of composite laminates.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

An experimentally validated analytical procedure has been used to study the transient response of simply supported, rectangular laminated composite plates subjected to low-speed impact loads. Both airgun-propelled and dropped-weight impactors were included in the study. The influence of transverse shear deformation on plate response for an airgun-propelled impactor is to advance the phase of the impact contact force and surface strain profiles even for low impact energy levels and to affect the magnitudes of surface strains for higher impact energy levels. This behavior is due to the short wave lengths of the local out-of-plane deflection associated with the impact event which decrease with increasing impact energy levels. For dropped-weight impactors, only the magnitude of the response is affected by not including transverse-shear effects. The analytical results agree well with the experimental results when transverse-shear effects are included in the analysis confirming the importance of including these secondary effects when studying the impact response of composite plates.

The geometrically nonlinear effects associated with large out-of-plane deformations are pronounced for simply supported laminates that are thinner than a 32-ply laminate for impact energies that are less than the impact energy necessary to initiate damage. Large errors in the response predictions for the thinner laminates were observed if a small-deformation theory is used for the analysis. When two opposite edges of a plate are clamped and the other two edges are simply supported, nonlinear effects are more pronounced than when all four edges are simply supported. These results indicate the need to include large-deformation effects and the appropriate boundary conditions in the analysis of composite plates in order to predict their low-speed impact response accurately.

REFERENCES

1. Sun, C. T., and Chattopadhyay, S., Dynamic Response of Anisotropic Laminated Plates Under Initial Stress to Impact of a Mass. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 42, September 1975, pp. 693-698.
2. Dobyns, A. L., Analysis of Simply-Supported Orthotropic Plates Subject to Static and Dynamic Loads. *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 19, No. 5, May 1981, pp. 642-650.
3. Ochoa, C. M., Nondimensional Models for Low Velocity Impact of Laminated Composite Panels. Proceedings of the AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS 28th Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, Monterey, CA, April 6-8, 1987, pp. 443-447. AIAA Paper No. 87-0802.
4. Shivakumar, K. N., Elber, W., and Illg, W., Prediction of Low-Velocity Impact Damage in Thin Circular Laminates. *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 23, No. 3, March 1985, pp. 442-449.
5. Christoforou, A. P., and Swanson, S. R., Analysis of Impact Response in Composite Plates. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 27, No. 2, 1991, pp. 161-170.
6. Olsson, R., Impact Response of Orthotropic Composite Plates Predicted from a One-Parameter Differential Equation. *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 10, No. 6, June 1992, pp. 1587-1596.
7. Ambur, D. R., Starnes, J. H., Jr., and Prasad, C. B., Influence of Transverse-Shear and Large- Deformation Effects on the Low-Speed Impact Response of Laminated Composite Plates. NASA TM-107753, April 1993.
8. Starnes, J. H., Jr., Rhodes, M. D., and Williams, J. G., Effect of Impact Damage and Holes on the Compressive Strength of a Graphite/Epoxy Laminate. *Nondestructive Evaluation and Flaw Criticality for Composite Materials*, ASTM STP 696, edited by R. B. Pipes, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, 1979, pp. 145-171.
9. Reddy, J. N., A Refined Nonlinear Theory of Plates with Transverse Shear Deformation. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 20, No. 9/10, 1984, pp. 881-896.

Fig. 1 Strain gage locations (all gages excepting gage 2B are located on the surface opposite to the impacted surface).

2(a) Longitudinal strain at plate center for an airgun impact with a 1.27-cm.-diameter steel ball with 1.42 J of impact energy.

2(b) Longitudinal strain at plate center for an airgun impact with a 1.27-cm.-diameter steel ball with 2.17 J of impact energy.

2(c) Deflection profile along y-axis at $x=6.35$ cm. after 30 μ sec for airgun impact with 1.42 J of impact energy from a 1.27-cm.-diameter steel ball.

2(d) Longitudinal strain at plate center for dropped-weight impact with a 1.27-cm.-diameter steel tip with 2.95 J of impact energy.

2(e) Longitudinal strain at plate center for dropped-weight impact with 1.27-cm.-diameter steel tip with 4.1 J of impact energy.

Fig. 2 Effects of transverse-shear deformation on the response of a 12.7-cm.-wide by 25.4-cm.-long graphite-epoxy plates subjected to lateral impact.

3(a) Comparison of measured strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 48-ply simply supported laminate subjected to 5.42 J of dropped-weight impact.

3(b) Comparison of analytical and experimental strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 24-ply simply supported laminated plate subjected to 1.36 J and 2.95 J of dropped-weight impact.

3(c) Comparison of analytical and experimental strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 24-ply simply supported laminated plate subjected to 4.1 J and 5.42 J of dropped-weight impact.

3(d) Comparison of analytical and experimental strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 32-ply simply supported laminated plate subjected to 1.36 J and 2.95 J of dropped-weight impact.

3(e) Comparison of analytical and experimental strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 32-ply simply supported laminated plate subjected to 4.1 J and 5.42 J of dropped-weight impact.

Fig. 3 Influence of large deformations on the impact response of 12.7-cm.-wide and 25.4-cm.-long laminated graphite-epoxy plates for increasing energy levels.

4(a) Comparison of measured strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 24-ply laminated plate with two different sets of boundary conditions subjected to dropped-weight impactors.

Fig. 4 Continued.

4(b) Comparison of measured strains on surface opposite to impact side in a 32-ply laminated plate with two different sets of boundary conditions subjected to dropped-weight impactors.

4(c) Comparison of measured membrane strains in a 24-ply laminated plate with two different sets of boundary conditions subjected to dropped-weight impactors.

Fig. 4 Effect of boundary conditions and large deformations on the impact response of laminated graphite-epoxy plates.

Fig. 4 Concluded.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEMS

